

The formation and evolution of stellar bars in cosmological simulations

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Galactic bars, Granada, July 3rd, 2023

What are the galaxy ingredients for the presence of a bar?

Cosmological Hydrodynamical Simulations

- Universe regions of ~ 100 Mpc in one side
- Galaxy formation subgrid physics included:
 - star formation
 - metallicity dependent-gas cooling
 - black hole growth,
 - SN and AGN feedback among others
- Subgrid physics has been calibrated to match the low redshift observables of galaxy population

The Illustris TNG simulations

Credit: TNG team; Weinberger et al., 2017, Nelson et al., 2017, Pillepich et al., 2018)

Bars at early times in the TNG simulations

Massive disc galaxies only included

Bar finder based on Fourier decomposition of face-on stellar surface density
Rosas-Guevara et al. 2022, TNG50 bars across redshift

Bars at early times in the TNG simulations

Rosas-Guevara et al. 2022, TNG50 bars across redshift

JWST Early CEERS Images of high-z bars, Guo, Jogee et al. 2022

Evolution of the bar fraction is almost flat and decreases with redshift when observational bias is included

Rosas-Guevara et al. 2022, see also Zana et al. 2022

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Higher Bar fraction with higher stellar mass

Gas to stellar mass fractions are lower in barred galaxies

Barred galaxies have lower star-forming activity

Star forming galaxies

weak bars

strong bars

no bars

Rosas-Guevara et al. 2020

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Rosas-Guevara et al. 2020

Evolution of strongly barred galaxies

Rosas Guevara et al. 2020

Consistent with Fraser-McKevie et al. 2020

Discs form earlier in massive barred galaxies

Rosas-Guevara et al.
2020, 2022

Early settling
of the
galactic disc

What are the galaxy ingredients for the presence of a bar?

Can bar structures be connected to the galaxy history?

Feedback processes matter: Results from Zoom-in simulations of Milky Way-like haloes

AGN feedback (energy released due to the gas accretion onto the BH) affect the formation of a bar in a Milky way Halo (Bonoli et. al. 2016, Spinoso et al. 2017)

Eris BH, Bonoli et al. 2016

Feedback processes matter: Results from Zoom-in MW simulations

SN feedback (energy released into the ISM due to star formation) affect the properties of a bar in a Milky way Halo (Zana et al., 2019)

Eris, Zana et al. 2019

Feedback processes matter: Results from Zoom-in MW simulations

AGN feedback changes the properties of the bar in a Milky way Halo (Fragkoudi et al 2020, Irodotous et al, 2022)

Stellar surface density

Auriga , Irodotous et al. 2022

Zoom-ins of Milky Way-like galaxies from TNG50

6 galaxies, each of them with 6 TNG physical models variations in total 36 simulations

Working progress, in collaboration with: Silvia Bonoli, Massimo Dotti, Ewald Puchwein, Sergio Contreras

Two main variations of models

- Variations in **the energy input of galactic winds** created from the death of massive stars
- Variations in **the BH physics**

More models to run with awarded CPU time in Marenostrum in Barcelona Supercomputer Center!

Galactic winds affects bar formation

Changing the strength of the winds generated by SNIa (i.e., Energy injection)

Galactic winds affects bar formation

Changing the strength of the winds generated by SNI_I (i.e., Energy injection)

Galactic winds affects bar formation

Changing the strength of the winds generated by SNI_I (i.e., Energy injection)

AGN feedback in quasar mode does not inhibit the formation of a bar

Fiducial

AGN feedback in quasar mode does not inhibit the formation of a bar

Fiducial

No black holes

AGN feedback in quasar mode does not inhibit the formation of a bar

Bar formation in the TNG simulations

ELN-criterion (Efstathiou et al. 1982) utilised in galaxy formation models (SAMs) to identify disc instabilities that contribute to formation of bar structures.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{V_{\max}}{(GM_{\text{disc}}/R_d)^{1/2}}$$

$\varepsilon \leq 1.1$ Unstable stellar discs

$\varepsilon > 1.1$ Hot component that is able to stabilise stellar discs

Bar formation in the TNG simulations

~75/80 percent of barred/ unbarred galaxies satisfy the ELN criterion (Massive galaxies with strong bars)

Izquierdo-Villalba et al. 2022

Barred galaxies that satisfy ELN-criterion

Unbarred galaxies that satisfy ELN-criterion

Conclusions

Cosmological Hydrodynamical simulations

A useful way to understand the connection between bars and the assembly history of spiral galaxies

Galaxy properties connected to a presence of a bar

- Redshift evolution of the bar fraction is almost flat, consistent with observational bias is included
- Disc galaxies with massive, dynamically-cold discs and low gas fractions holds a bar.
- Barred galaxies formed earlier than unbarred galaxies with the same stellar

Feedback Processes matters for bar formation

- Galactic winds delay the settling of the massive, cold disc disc using MW-zoom ins simulations